

FORMATION OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: *Important reforms for the development of foreign languages are being implemented in Uzbekistan. In particular, since the years of independence, both leaders of the country have been paying serious attention to this issue. The fact that the development of the industry is being reformed by means of relevant regulatory documents, and the representatives of this industry are being supported in every way is a clear proof of our opinion. This article represents the formation of lexical competence using authentic materials. The importance of teaching the English language in non-philological institutions approaches to material selection, design, and implementation mainly focused on supporting ideas.*

Keywords: *lexical competence, foreign language, authentic material, material design, education, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), non-philological directions, development, authenticity, research, audience.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ

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Аннотация: *В Узбекистане реализуются важные реформы по развитию иностранных языков. В частности, с первых лет независимости оба руководителя страны уделяют этому вопросу серьезное внимание. Тот факт, что развитие отрасли реформируется посредством соответствующих нормативных документов, а представители этой отрасли всячески поддерживаются, является ярким подтверждением нашего мнения. В данной статье представлено формирование лексической компетенции с использованием аутентичных материалов, важность преподавания английского языка в нефилологических вузах, подходы к выбору, проектированию и реализации материалов, которые в основном ориентированы на поддержку идей.*

Ключевые слова: *лексическая компетентность, иностранный язык, аутентичный материал, оформление материала, образование, английский язык для специальных целей (ESP), нефилологические направления, развитие, аутентичность, исследование, аудитория.*

NOFILOLOGIK TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA INGLIZ TILI O'QITISHDA LEKSIK KOMPETENSIYANI AUTENTIK MATERIALLARDAN FOYDALANIB SHAKLLANTIRISH

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***Annotatsiya:** O'zbekistonda xorijiy tillarni rivojlantirish borasida muhim islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, mustaqillik yillaridan buyon davlat rahbarlari bu masalaga jiddiy e'tibor qaratib kelmoqda. Soha rivoji tegishli me'yoriy hujjatlar orqali isloh etilayotgani, soha vakillari har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlanayotgani fikrimizning yorqin dalilidir. Ushbu maqola haqiqiy materiallardan foydalangan holda leksik kompetensiyani shakllantirishni ifodalaydi. Nofilologik muassasalarda ingliz tilini o'qitishning ahamiyati material tanlash, loyihalash va amalga oshirishga yondashuvlar asosan g'oyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlashga qaratilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** leksik kompetensiya, chet tili, leksik kompetensiya, autentik material, material dizayni, ta'lim, maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), filologik bo'lmagan yo'nalishlar, rivojlanish, haqiqiylik, tadqiqot, auditoriya.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the need to learn foreign languages is one of the issues on a global scale and is becoming more and more important. It is not secret that language serves as the main bridge in strengthening economic and political relations between countries. Studying foreign languages not only broadens students' worldview, but also helps them to understand their own cultures more deeply. Language learning improves students' English language skills. Studying foreign languages increases listening skills and memory, strengthens the ability to analyze, develops the ability to solve problems and work with abstract concepts. And this, in turn, has been proven to strengthen mastery of other subjects [1]. From this point of view, the teaching and learning of foreign languages is viewed as an urgent task of state importance in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Important reforms for the development of foreign languages are being implemented. In particular, since the years of independence, both leaders of the country have been paying serious attention to this issue. The fact that the development of the industry is being reformed by means of relevant regulatory documents, and the representatives of this industry are being supported in every way is a clear proof of our opinion. Since 2012, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan has provided incentive payments and grants to foreign language teachers and teachers of the Ministry of Public Education, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education, and the Ministry of Finance, when calculating the allowances, it is determined to add monthly allowances in the amount of 30 percent to their tariff rates in educational institutions located in rural areas and 15 percent rates in other educational institutions, including

their salaries[2], and by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, starting from the 2021-2022 academic year, foreign languages (English, French, German, Spanish, Italian) of educational institutions with at least C1 level national or equivalent internationally recognized certificate, Arabic, Chinese, Japanese, Korean, Turkish, Persian, Pashto, Dari, Urdu, Hindi) teachers will be paid an additional monthly premium of 50 percent compared to their basic tariff rate, 2022/2023 academic year from 2015, the procedure for participation of persons with national or international certificates of the corresponding level in competitions for master's degrees and post-higher education specialties of higher education institutions should be introduced. In this case, at least a C1 level national or equivalent international certificate for philological fields, and a B2 level national or equivalent international certificate for non-philological fields are required for foreign language teachers and other representatives of the field [3] have tasked with doing more research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the world experience, various researches are being carried out and improved in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions. According to Hutchinson and Waters studies [4, 18-19], English language teaching for special purposes (hereinafter ESP) is one of the important types of language teaching. They focus on ESP for specialist subjects, specifically English language teaching in technology-oriented educational institutions, as well as scientific vocabulary and grammar for scientists. It does not differ from other forms of language learning according to the principles of quick and effective learning. It is an approach to language learning that based on the needs of the learner and guided by specific and specific reasons for learning.

In our previous studies, we focused on teaching English for special purposes in detail. In particular, English for Specific Purposes or ESP (English for Specific Purposes) refers to the teaching and learning of English with a view to using it in a specific field, where the goal of students is to acquire English in a specific academic, professional field. English for Professional Purposes (EOP) and EAP (English for Academic Purposes) [5, 20]. Development of lexical competence for non-philological purposes is important in improving all skills. In this research, we aim to study the importance of authentic materials in the development of lexical competence. Competence is knowledge in one or another field. "Competence" (lat. *competo* - I am achieving, I am worthy, I deserve) - 1) the range of powers, rights and duties of a certain state body (local self-government body) or official defined by law, charter or other document; 2) knowledge, experience in this or that field. Lexical competence is the competence in understanding words, understood as a component of general semantic competence. The research conducted in this regard focuses on the formation of skills aimed at special conversation in a certain field of science, reading and listening to authentic texts, working with specialized articles, as well as writing special texts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The issue of developing lexical competence using authentic materials in teaching foreign languages is not a new topic. Several foreign and local scientists have conducted a number of researches in this regard. For example, Nunan and Miller (1995) define authentic materials as "not designed or edited specifically for language learners." According to them, authentic materials show how native English speakers use English. This means that most everyday objects in the target language can be evaluated as authentic materials and used not only for general English but also for ESP learning/teaching.[6] Authentic materials are available in unlimited quantities. Finding them depends on the ingenuity of the searchers. In the following, table some types and sources of authentic materials offered:

Table 1

Forms of authentic sources

Daily objects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business cards • bank statements • pictures • Checks • catalogs • currencies • financial records • guidelines • bank accounts • application forms • pictures • list forms • letters/email • diagrams • contracts • brochures • bank instructions
Media world and the Internet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • newspapers • magazines • TV and radio broadcasts • movies • documentaries • internet websites • general and special literature
Websites that are easy to access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • authentic publications on the field • statistics

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• report• questionnaire
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Above, scientists classified authentic materials according to the results of their research and observations and emphasized their importance. In our opinion, authentic material is original material developed for any non-pedagogical purpose, freely available, free of any censorship and restrictions. In some sources, authentic materials are referred to as "original", "genuine" materials or sources. But, we believe that none of the above expressions correspond to the original content of the authentic materials. We believe that the terms "authentic" and "authenticity" are a single lexical unit that is not changed in meaning and cannot be translated. It is natural that some problems arise when using authentic materials for pedagogical purposes. The reason is that, as mentioned above, these materials do not have any restrictions, aesthetic or aesthetic treatments. It is advisable to use them in the order in which they were created. Treatment of authentic materials, removal of certain parts undermines their originality. From this point of view, real pedagogues should always keep in mind that their use in the auditorium causes a number of inconveniences to the teacher and the student. It is closely related to the concepts of mentality and etiquette. Let us say the teacher is using an authentic video as an authentic material in the classroom. Showing potentially inappropriate scenes in the video may create an uncomfortable situation for the audience. It has been proven that such situations seriously affect the effectiveness of education not only in the Uzbek audience, which has its own values, but also in Western audiences. Therefore, it is advisable to take into account all aspects in the selection and selection of authentic materials. We plan to address potentially controversial content issues in more detail in future chapters of our research.

We are going to touch briefly on the status of using authentic tools in English language classes. Today, there are different approaches to using authentic materials in English classes. We can say that science programs in educational institutions partially cover authentic materials.

UzSWLU scientist P.Kh.Omanov selected authentic video materials in the object of his research on the development of socio-cultural competence of students and connected the typology of exercises he recommended directly with the stages of the process of showing video materials. He considered it appropriate to organize work with exercises and assignments in three main stages: before the performance, during the performance, and after the performance. During the presentation of authentic video materials, students perform certain exercises and tasks that are located between episodes. This helps the students to deeply feel and understand the content of the videos. It was also noted that in the process of authentic video materials, students will be given the task of setting up 2 different observation processes:

1. Sociolinguistic observation: - observing the characteristics of the interlocutors (age, gender, origin, socio-economic status, field of professional activity, etc.),

analyzing the selection of speech units and extralinguistic tools and their impact on the speech process; - analysis of the accent, speed of speech characteristics of the interlocutors in accordance with the socio-cultural characteristics (in the example of the dialects of the USA, Great Britain, the native language of the speakers)

2. Socio-cultural observation: 1) identifying words of a socio-cultural nature, determining in which socio-cultural situations words of a socio-cultural nature are used. 2) to describe the equivalents in the mother tongue and in what socio-cultural situations they are used. 3) to identify social situations, to analyze expressions specific to social situations. [7, 821]

Unfortunately, there is a lack of systematic research on the development of lexical competence using authentic materials in non-philological higher educational institutions. In this regard, scientists in Uzbekistan have emphasized this issue in their scientific work. For example, in her doctoral thesis, D.M. Israilova defined the components of communicative and intercultural communication competence of engineering students according to modern pedagogical approaches, focusing on the field (narrowing) aimed at developing students' linguistic and communicative skills and mastering authentic educational material.[8, 11].

And K.Sh. Muradkasimova recognized that in improving the competence of future specialists, the teacher should focus on five principles in order to know whether the assessment is effective, connected to the course content, useful and authentic. These principles serve as the main criteria for evaluating the appropriateness of the type of assessment. These are practicality, reliability, validity, washback, and authenticity. In addition, he referred to an authentic type of assessment. In particular, the ability of students to demonstrate their acquired knowledge in real life situations. The main concept of this type of assessment is a model, practice and feedback, not parts, but a practice-oriented model of the whole concept. Different methods can be used in authentic assessment. The purpose of authentic assessment is to enable students to effectively use their knowledge and analyze their own actions. [9, 40]

Despite the fact that these ideas stimulate important changes in the teaching of English in non-philological higher educational institutions, they do not provide sufficient information on the development of lexical competence using authentic materials.

In our previous study, we recommended a science program consisting of 5 modules for the development of lexical competence in agricultural areas. This science program provides partial guidance on the use of authentic materials. Including useful additional materials - Teachers should try to use authentic materials whenever possible. Teachers must take the time to identify and adapt authentic materials for use in the classroom. Authentic materials relevant to this module include text types. All these are available on the internet or in the local industry. Each module includes examples of formative (authentic) and summative (pedagogical) assessment tasks. Formative

assessment should include information about people, context, and goals. That is, the main content of the evaluation should be taken from real-life tools, it is clear to whom, for what and for what purpose. Nevertheless, there is a need to conduct research on the importance of authentic materials in the development of lexical competence through deeper analysis. The reason is that, as mentioned above, authentic materials are highly effective in the teaching process, but also have several disadvantages. Before applying them to the educational process, it is important to carefully select them, sort them, and form them based on a balanced methodology.

According to L.P. Ruiz and K.S. Molinero, as in all areas of ESP, the English language has become a means of expressing engineering knowledge. Therefore, in the eyes of students, this language has become a real program. However, even though students already know the language, they are realizing that there is a gap in their knowledge of English for Special Purposes-ESP. That is, they know engineering and language to some extent, but in this respect, they lack fluency and accuracy in using English. There are not textbooks that specifically address the requirements of any particular engineering field when considering materials used in this type of audience and for specific needs. Additionally, there is a dearth of published material that provides the specificity or depth of information required at higher levels. On the other hand, authentic materials have been shown to meet the needs of students within their scope, engaging them in the real world of English language use within the context of their reading and delivery purposes [10,183]. These scientists introduced the concept of "ESP-English for Specific Purposes" as "EST-English for Science and Technology". This shows that ESP is not just a branch of language teaching, but it has become one of the systematic directions that develop science, technology and development. European scientists have already approached this issue seriously and are conducting research related to the development of the science network.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

Unfortunately, in Uzbekistan, the network of teaching English for special purposes is still taught in combination with philological directions. In the science programs of non-philology educational institutions, resources and materials for teaching general English added to course syllabuses. From this point of view, first, it is desirable to create a set of science programs for use in English language classes of non-philological higher education institutions.

In conclusion, it can be noted that it is important to determine the educational needs first in the formation of the software and materials base for teaching English in non-philological higher educational institutions. Although some research has been done in teaching English for special purposes, there is still a lot of research to be done on integrating the authentic material base into the educational process. In this regard, significant studies have been conducted in foreign scientific publications. It is inevitable that their application in non-philological higher education in accordance with

the development of English language lexical competence will guarantee the further development of the field.

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